

A pilot study to classify salt treated poplar plants using machine learning algorithms

Bushra Jalil*, Iqra Sarfraz†, Lorenzo Della Maggiora†, Alessandra Francini†, Luca Valcarengi*, Luca Sebastiani†

* TeCIP institute, Scuola Superiore Sant’Anna, Pisa, Italy

† Crop Science Research Center, Scuola Superiore Sant’Anna, Pisa, Italy

e-mail: bushra.jalil@santannapisa.it

Abstract—In recent times, salinity has emerged as a significant abiotic stress affecting plant survival in an ecosystem. In the experimental setup, response to salinity was investigated in *Populus alba* L. ‘Villafranca’ clone transgenic plants (line 16, 22 and 24) over-expressing an aquaporin – *aqual* – and compared to *P. alba* wild-type (Wt). Plants were grown *in vivo* under both control conditions (0 mM NaCl) and salinity (100 mM NaCl) for the duration of 28 days. This work presents a pilot study to investigate the performance of machine learning based algorithms to classify poplar leaves exposed to salt stress treatment, with the aim of performing the task in automated manner. The data set used in this work contains images acquired through a normal RGB camera. Segmentation and normalization based pre-processing were applied on the complete data set. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) based architectures were employed for the extraction of prominent features from the images. Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Logistic Regression (LR) classified the extracted feature into the group of plants treated with 100 mM NaCl or otherwise. The primary evaluation index, accuracy indicates that the classification with SVM and RF achieved highest accuracy 75% and 71% to detect leaves of 100 mM NaCl treated plants.

Index Terms—Poplar, Salt stress, Convolution Neural Networks, Random Forest, Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machine, Classification

I. INTRODUCTION

Poplar belongs to *Salicaceae* family and it is known to be a fast growing tree in the group of woody perennial plants. It is studied as a model species for investigating tree response to environmental stresses. Poplars are also known as providers of forest commodities such as wood, fuel wood and fiber. In addition, they are involved in the re-integration and renewal of degraded landscapes [1]. Climate change has given rise to various ecological and environmental challenges and salt stress is one of the most significant ones [2]. Osmotic stress, nutrient imbalance, ion toxicity and stomatal closure are the main effects of salinity on plant growth. These stresses, when combined, cause metabolic imbalance, resulting in oxidative stress and eventually cell death. In recent years, there has been a significant increase in the study of plant response to salinity [3]. Traditionally, understanding plant response to different abiotic stresses, particularly salinity, demanded expensive and time-consuming laboratory procedures. However, with the recent advancement in the field of artificial based technologies, various opportunities have emerged in the field of agriculture to automate the monitoring process in the

form of precision agriculture. There has been a substantial advancement in the application of machine learning algorithms in other fields as well, such as in robotics, health monitoring and environmental monitoring that could also be used for agriculture and currently, precision agriculture became an essential component of the modern agriculture. Edge computing and artificial intelligence based monitoring systems are frequently used due to their precise performance and low cost. Not only that, these systems allow monitoring by situating at remote location with the aid of the sensors deployed in the field for this purpose. In this regard, several methods using artificial intelligence based technologies have been proposed during last few years. Van Dijk *et al.* reviewed some of these techniques applied in various plant science applications ranging from biochemical to macroscopic levels and how machine learning based methods can help in finding the meaningful patterns in plant data [4]. They also discussed the applications of machine learning and suggested future research directions. Ali *et al.* presented an automated leaf recognition method for plant identification. The proposed technique is based on a combination of two types of texture features, named bag-of-features and Local binary pattern, and decision-making model that is based on a SVM classifier [5]. A considerable number of methods for plant stress research is based on machine learning algorithms aimed at the identification, classification and prediction of salt stressed plants. Among them, one of the pipeline proposed by Kecoglu *et al.* is based on a combination of machine learning and Raman spectroscopy based methods to analyse biochemical change that occurs while the medium salt concentration changes and predicts the level of salt stress [6]. Similarly, Yao *et al.* presented a method to classify the salt tolerance of wheat plant. They predicted the plant electrical signals by using 1-dimensional CNNs based models under long-term stress with different NaCl concentrations [7]. Also, Das *et al.* performed identification and classification of salinity stress in rice plant using supervised machine learning algorithms including KNN, XGB, *etc.* based remote sensing [8]. Moghimi *et al.* presented an ensemble feature selection method to identify spectral features for practical applications in plant phenotyping using a hyper spectral data set containing the images of four wheat lines, each with a control and a salt (NaCl) treatment. They investigated the ability of spectral features to discriminate salt-stressed wheat plants

Fig. 1. Representation of 0 mM NaCl and 100 mM NaCl treated plant leaves from Wt, line 16, line 22 and line 24.

from healthy plants at the earliest stages of stress [9]. There exist several other methods to depict the response of external stimuli (stresses) in various types of plants but there exists a limited study to investigate poplar response to salt stress with artificial intelligence based algorithms. Therefore, this work presents a pilot study to investigate the detection of *P.alba* "Villafranca" plant exposed to salt stress stimulus and respective outcome after 28 days by using artificial intelligence-based techniques. The methodology is mainly based on pre-trained Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), as a feature extractor to extract significant features from the leaves of both classes, 0 mM NaCl and 100 mM NaCl, by convolving training images through multiple 2-dimensional filters. After feature extraction, supervised learning-based classifiers were employed for classification purposes. The complete model was trained on the provided dataset and validated with the test data. The classification step grouped the features extracted via CNNs based architectures to distinct groups of unique characteristics termed as classes. The machine learning based algorithms studied in this work included Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Logistic Regression (LR).

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: the methodology of the processing is given in section II. Theoretical background of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) architecture based feature extraction in section III. In section IV, the detailed explanation of machine learning based classifiers is presented. Section V presents the comparative analysis and performance of the classifiers. Section VI concludes the paper with future extension.

II. METHODOLOGY

The methodology studied in this paper is based on pre-trained CNNs as a feature extractor and supervised learning based classifiers to distinguish salt treated plants. After splitting the data into training and testing, pre-processing was applied. In machine learning, two approaches are mainly used for the classification purposes where input can be pixel values or extracted features. The significant features were extracted

using pre-trained network in transfer learning scheme. The network extracted the features through the series of 2-dimensional filters and identified the points of interest from the given data set, termed as features extraction. The classification step grouped the features extracted via CNNs based architectures into two classes, 0 mM NaCl and 100 mM NaCl. In the coming sections, the detail methodology and processing is presented.

Fig. 2. Pre-processing applied to 0 mM NaCl and 100 mM NaCl treated plant leaves: a) Original leaf, b) Mask obtained through the color channels and c) Final segmented leaf.

A. Plant growth and NaCl treatment

All the 24 plants from Wt and transgenic lines (line 16, 22 and 24) were grown *in vitro* and acclimatized *in vivo* for six weeks in growth chamber under controlled environmental conditions (23:18°C Day:Night temperature, 65% to 70% relative humidity and 16h photoperiod at a photosynthetic photon flux density of $400 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ supplied by fluorescent lights. In April, plants were transferred into plastic pots containing a mixture of 8-20 \AA mm expanded Agrileca clay (Laterlite, Milano - Italy) and sand (50/50 v/v) and placed outdoor according to a completely randomized blocks design in a space in which they were protected from rain.

Granular fertilizer was provided to each plant, and tap water was used to water them. After one month of growth, before starting the salt treatment, plants reached an average height of 34.2 ± 7.8 cm and an average number of leaves of 18 ± 3 . Plants of each line ($n = 6$) were randomly divided in two groups: control plants (CP) and treated plants (TP). CP received tap water for four weeks, while TP received tap water supplemented with a concentration of 100 mM NaCl.

Fig. 3. Schematic illustration of NaCl treated plants classification pipeline.

The same volume of water (containing or not containing the salt) was provided to each plant three times per week. At the end of the 28 days treatment period, TP received 24 g of sodium chloride. During the experiment, several physiological and morphological analysis were performed. Pictures of Wt and transgenic line leaves were taken from TP and CP at the end of the stress treatment.

B. Data Set and Pre-processing

Twenty-four plants of *Populus alba* L. “Villafranca” clone were used in the experiment. Wildtype plants (Wt, $n = 6$) and plants from three transgenic lines previously transformed [10] and over-expressing a tonoplast poplar aquaporin from *Populus x euramericana* “I-214” clone were studied (line 16, line 22 and line 24; $n = 6$ for each line). Control and treated plants of each line were sampled after 28 days from the start of the NaCl treatment. The leaf images were acquired with a normal RGB camera, resolution of 4160×3120 , in normal daylight conditions. Each line consisted of 30 images for a total of 120 images. Fig.1 represents some of the acquired images with and without 100 mM NaCl treatment. The initial pre-processing of the data set includes the removal of the background using threshold based segmentation to extract ROI and resizing of all images to reduce computational cost as shown in Fig.2. For the feature extraction, data normalization is performed as it directly influences the performance of the predictive model where the data values of the features differ significantly. Although some techniques *e.g.*, RF are more robust but to perform the comparative analysis, data pre-processing is applied prior to the training step. The schematic illustration of the processing is given in Fig. 3.

III. CNN BASED FEATURE EXTRACTION

Feature selection is the process of finding optimal data points which represent given set of data. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) based feature learning is commonly used in several applications. These networks take advantage of the spatial information of the images *e.g.*, their structure and local properties. Currently, CNNs are the most extensively studied network architecture, which can take in an input image, assign weights and biases to the objects in the image and differentiate them from each other with better accuracy as compared to the other classification algorithms. Gu *et al.* provided an

extensive survey of the recent advances in the field of CNNs [11]. The convolutional layers learn feature representation of the inputs and composed of several convolution kernels to compute different feature maps. Specifically, each neuron of a feature map is connected to a region of neighbouring neurons in the previous layer [11]. The new feature map can be obtained by first convolving the input with a learned kernel and then applying an element-wise nonlinear activation function on the convolved results and to generate each feature map, the kernel is shared by all spatial locations of the input [11]. The complete feature maps are obtained by using several different kernels. Mathematically, the feature value at location (i, j) in the k -th feature map of l -th layer, $z_{i,j,k}^l$, is calculated by [11]:

$$z_{i,j,k}^l = w_k^{lT} x_{i,j}^l + b_k^l \quad (1)$$

where w_k^l and b_k^l are the weight vector and bias term of the k -th filter of the l -th layer respectively, and $x_{i,j}^l$ is the input patch centered at location (i, j) of the l -th layer [11]. The activation value $a_{i,j,k}^l$ of convolutional feature $z_{i,j,k}^l$ can be computed as [11]:

$$a_{i,j,k}^l = a(z_{i,j,k}^l) \quad (2)$$

The pooling layers aggregate information within the feature map by replacing local pooling regions with the maximum element in the case of max pooling. The model pre-trained on the features of 1.2 million training images from 1000 classes of Image Net data is employed as a fixed feature extractor, where the weights of the networks are frozen.

IV. CLASSIFICATION ALGORITHMS

Machine learning classifiers are used to classify the leaf images as salt treated or control on the set of extracted features to fit the data. The supervised learning algorithms studied in this work are widely used in other classification tasks due to their precise performance. The brief overview of these classifiers is discussed in the following section.

A. Support Vector Machine (SVM)

SVM is a supervised machine learning algorithm that can be used for both linear and non-linear separable features. Traditionally, the algorithm selects the surface that lies equidistant

from the nearest vector spaces and classifies the dataset in classes by calculating the margin between each class with support vectors [12]. For several classes, the most common algorithm is based on “one versus all” approach where a classifier is trained for each class. In this work, *RBF kernel*, commonly used in SVM classification problems is used [12].

The *RBF kernel* on two samples u and v , represented as feature vectors in the input space, is defined as [12]:

$$k(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) = \exp\left(-\frac{\|u - v\|^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (3)$$

where $\|u - v\|$ is the squared Euclidean distance between the feature vectors, and σ is a regularisation parameter. The value of the *RBF kernel* decreases with the distance and ranges between zero and one, and the RBF kernel maps the data into an infinite-dimensional space.

B. Random Forest (RF)

Random Forest is a supervised, ensemble machine learning algorithm that integrates multiple trees through the bagging idea [13], [14]. The predictions of all those decision trees are then taken into consideration for a voting criterion and the predicted output of the classifier is the class with maximum votes. In this study, hyper parameters e.g. estimators, depth are determined by using grid search methods. The classifier uses Ginni Index for attribute selection, it gauges the impurity of an attribute with respect to classes [14]. For a given dataset T , selecting one item of the data set (pixel) at random and telling that the item is belonging to class C_i , the Ginni Index can be written as:

$$Obj = \sum_{j=1} \sum \left(\frac{f(C_i, T)}{|T|} \right) \left(\frac{f(C_j, T)}{|T|} \right) \quad (4)$$

where $\frac{f(C_i, T)}{|T|}$ is the probability that the selected case belongs to class C_i

C. Logistic Regression (LR)

Logistic Regression is considered as an effective and widely used method for binary classification problems. LR establishes a regression formula and a sigmoid function nested based on this multiple linear regression model [12]. In LR, given N instances x_i , where $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$, the m features of the input instance $\mathbf{x}_i = (x_{i1}, x_{i2}, \dots, x_{im})$, are combined linearly using coefficients β_0 and $\beta_i = (\beta_{i1}, \beta_{i2}, \dots, \beta_{im})$ to predict the classification outcome y_i . Specifically, given an input instance \mathbf{x}_i , the probability that $y_i = 1$ is denoted by $p(\mathbf{x}_i)$ and is modelled with the standard logistic regression model as follows [12]:

$$p(\mathbf{x}_i) = \left\{ \frac{e^{(\beta_0 + \beta * \mathbf{x}_i)}}{1 + e^{(\beta_0 + \beta * \mathbf{x}_i)}} \right\} \quad (5)$$

The aim of LR is to find the best parameters β_0 and β to determine the best fitting model that describes the relationship between the input features and the predicted class value [12].

Fig. 4. Statistics of the Accuracy index (%) of each algorithm.

V. SIMULATIONS AND DISCUSSION

During the experimentation period, several images of leaves were collected along with the morphological and physiological data collection. Collected images were then analyzed using machine learning to identify the differences between the control (0 mM NaCl) and the treated group (100 mM NaCl). The analysis resulted in an accuracy of 70% in differentiating between salt-stressed and non-stressed groups. The conventional approach for measuring different plant parameters such as chlorophyll content, chlorophyll a fluorescence and leaf gas exchanges as shown in Fig. 5 is time-consuming and physically demanding as it requires measuring each leaf individually. This becomes specifically challenging when dealing with a considerably large number of plants. Therefore, in this work, we presented a pilot study to develop an approach which can categorize the plants using normal colored images. Image data acquired through normal smartphone camera offer a potentially effective solution for rapid data collection, ensuring efficient analysis of various parameters such as chlorophyll content within a short period of time.

Fig. 5. Example of the current method for chlorophyll, gas exchanges, and other parameters measurement in poplar leaves: A. Measure of chlorophyll content through a SPAD meter, B: Measure of gas exchanges through a portable photosynthesis system (CIRAS)

This work presents the comparative analysis of well-known network architectures including DenseNet121 and VGG19

Fig. 6. Normalized confusion matrices of SVM, RF and LR.

with traditional machine learning classifiers for the classification of salt treated poplar leaves. Wild-type and transgenic line plants grown under similar conditions for 28 days (control or treatment), were phenotypically indistinguishable. No morphological differences were observed, even though *aqual* gene expression levels in line 16, 22 and 24 were different compared to Wt plants. Images acquired during experiment were then investigated with AI based algorithms to distinguish two classes. Pre-trained networks were trained using Keras on top of Tensor Flow 2.2 environment. The weights of both architectures, directly obtained from Keras library were trained as a fixed feature extractor scheme on current data set. On top of the fixed feature extraction layers, machine learning classifiers learn underlying patterns through features extracted from training set and discriminate data accordingly. To evaluate the performance of the classification algorithms, accuracy, precision and F1 score were considered as evaluation parameters. *Accuracy* refers to the proportion of all correctly predicted outcome (including positive samples and negative samples) in the total data and *Precision* represents the correct positive predictions [15]:

$$Accuracy = \left\{ \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \right\} \quad (6)$$

$$Precision = \left\{ \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \right\} \quad (7)$$

Recall is the number of correct positive predictions divided by the number of positive results that should have been returned. *F1-score* is obtained by the weighted harmonic average of precision and recall due to the contradiction between the two evaluation indexes and is formulated as [15]:

$$F1 = \left\{ \frac{2PR}{P + R} \right\} \quad (8)$$

Fig. 4 summarizes the evaluation of models on the test data with the classification techniques. Among the traditional machine learning classifiers, SVM achieved highest accuracy 75% by using DenseNet as a feature extraction model, followed by the RF with the accuracy of 72%. Similarly, feature extracted

Class	SVM	RF	LR
Precision(%)			
NaCl 0mM	72.22	66.67	66.67
NaCl 100mM	78.57	81.82	71.43
Recall(%)			
NaCl 0mM	81.25	87.5	75
NaCl 100mM	68.75	56.25	62.5
F1 score(%)			
NaCl 0mM	76.47	75.68	70.59
NaCl 100mM	73.33	66.67	66.67

Fig. 7. Class-wise precision of classifiers, recall and F1 score on the test data.

with VGG19 architecture achieved comparable accuracy of 68.75% using LR as a classifier. To examine the class-wise performance, Fig. 7 illustrate the numerical outcome of ML classifier in terms of precision, recall and F1-score using the total of 120 images for training and testing purposes. In general, 72% of the plant leaves treated with 100 mM NaCl were identified and among them 69% of the treated plant leaves were correctly identified with SVM. Similarly 81% of the non-treated leaves were also correctly identified with SVM. Fig. 6 shows the normalized confusion matrices of the classification scheme, where all the proposed methodological schemes, on average 80% of the plant leaves, not treated with NaCl 100 mM were correctly classified. However, as explained before, no significant morphological differences were observed during the experimental phase and, as a result, on average approximately 62% of 100 mM NaCl treated plant leaves were correctly classified. As this work is presented as a pilot study to analyze poplar plants with limited data set and while experimentation there is in-significant class variance between two groups but in future, with large data set and by applying augmentation techniques, the objective is to improve the accuracy and to test these methods on other plants treated with salt stress.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this study, the response of *Populus alba* "Villafranca" clone to salinity was investigated, as salinity is one of the factors responsible for reducing plant growth and survival. Images collected during the experimentation period were further analyzed with machine learning based classifiers. Pre-trained Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) were used as a feature extractor to extract significant features of both groups, 0 mM NaCl and 100 mM NaCl. Supervised learning-based three classification algorithms were studied to distinguish the extracted features. The obtained test accuracy was 75% using SVM, 71% using RF and 68% using LR. On average 80% of the plant leaves, not treated with 100 mM NaCl were correctly classified. However, due to insignificant class variance observed during the experiment 62% of the investigated NaCl 100 mM treated plant leaves were correctly classified. In future, by acquiring more data set at each stage and with different illumination conditions, we intend to apply other color transformation schemes and with deep neural models, thus improving the classification accuracy to differentiate salt treated plants.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was partly supported by the project CLEVER (Project ID 101097560), that is supported by the Key Digital Technologies Joint Undertaking and its members (including top-up funding by Italian Ministry of University and Research — MUR), in part by "MUR Programma Operativo Nazionale (PON) Ricerca e Innovazione 2014-2020" and in part by "VIRMA: Velivolo Intelligente Robotico per il Monitoraggio Agro-Ambientale - finanziato dal MUR nell'ambito del Fondo per la promozione e lo sviluppo delle politiche del Programma nazionale per la ricerca PNR, in coerenza con il Regolamento UE n. 241/2021 e con il PNRR 2021-2026, misura: Iniziative di ricerca interdisciplinare che esplorino temi di rilievo trasversale per il PNR, senza restrizioni basate sull'aderenza a settori scientifici di riferimento o ad aree tematiche prioritarie"

REFERENCES

- [1] Biselli C, Vietto L, Rosso L, Cattivelli L, Nervo G, Fricano A. Advanced Breeding for Biotic Stress Resistance in Poplar. *Plants* (Basel). 2022 Aug 4;11(15):2032. doi: 10.3390/plants11152032. PMID: 35956510; PMCID: PMC9370193.
- [2] Sharma, Akhilesh and Rana, Chanchal and Singh, Saurabh and Katoch, Viveka. (2016). Soil Salinity Causes, Effects, and Management in Cucurbits.
- [3] Hamed, Mahdi, Golkar, Pooran and Arzani A., In vitro Salt Tolerance of Safflower (*Carthamus tinctorius* L.) Genotypes using Different Explants. *Plant Tissue Culture and Biotechnology*. 26. 231, 2016.
- [4] Van Dijk ADJ, Kootstra G, Kruijer W, de Ridder D. Machine learning in plant science and plant breeding. *iScience*. 2020 Dec 5;24(1):101890. doi: 10.1016/j.isci.2020.101890. PMID: 33364579; PMCID: PMC7750553
- [5] R. Ali, R. Hardie and A. Essa, "A Leaf Recognition Approach to Plant Classification Using Machine Learning," NAECON 2018 - IEEE National Aerospace and Electronics Conference, Dayton, OH, USA, 2018, pp. 431-434, doi: 10.1109/NAECON.2018.8556785.
- [6] Kecoglu, I., Sirkeci, M., Unlu, M.B. et al. Quantification of salt stress in wheat leaves by Raman spectroscopy and machine learning. *Sci Rep* 12, 7197 (2022).

- [7] Jie-Peng Yao, Zi-Yang Wang, Ricardo Ferraz de Oliveira, Zhong-Yi Wang, Lan Huang, A deep learning method for the long-term prediction of plant electrical signals under salt stress to identify salt tolerance, *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, Volume 190, 2021, 106435,
- [8] Das, B.; Manohara, K.; Mahajan, G.; Sahoo, R.N. Spectroscopy Based Novel Spectral Indices, PCA-and PLSR-Coupled Machine Learning Models for Salinity Stress Phenotyping of Rice. *Spectrochim. Acta Part A Mol. Biomol. Spectrosc.* 2020, 229, 117983.
- [9] Moghimi, Ali, Yang, Ce, Marchetto, Peter, Ensemble Feature Selection for Plant Phenotyping: A Journey From Hyperspectral to Multispectral Imaging. *IEEE Access*. PP. 1-1, 2018.
- [10] Ariani A, Francini A, Andreucci A, Sebastiani L. Over-expression of AQUA1 in *Populus alba* Villafranca clone increases relative growth rate and water use efficiency, under Zn excess condition. *Plant Cell Rep.* 2016 Feb;35(2):289-301. doi: 10.1007/s00299-015-1883-9. Epub 2015 Oct 30. PMID: 26518428.
- [11] Gu, J. et al., "Recent advances in convolutional neural networks", *Pattern Recognition*, 2018, 77, 354–377.
- [12] Annalisa Occhipinti et al., "A pipeline and comparative study of 12 machine learning models for text classification", *Expert Systems with Applications*, Volume 201, 2022, 117193,
- [13] L. Breiman, "Random forests," *Machine Learning*, vol. 45, no. 1, pp. 5–32, 2001.
- [14] R. S. Chugh et al., "A Comparative Analysis of Classifiers for Image Classification," *10th International Conference on Cloud Computing, Data Science and Engineering*, Noida, India, 2020, pp. 248-253,
- [15] M. Hossin and S. Mn, "A review on evaluation metrics for data classification evaluations", *International Journal of Data Mining and Knowledge Management Process*, vol. 5, no. 2, 2015.